

Shiny4SelfReport

– a free self-reporting app for the management of fisheries

Self-reporting applications are a promising solution for monitoring in fisheries, letting the fishers **report catch while still at sea**. The Shiny4SelfReport is a new, flexible self-reporting app.

The tool was designed to be simple and adaptable, aimed to fill gaps in the management of fisheries in developing countries.

Shiny4Self Report was **designed with the user in mind**, aiming to provide an easy solution for fishers, management and researchers alike.

Though designed for fisheries, the framework can be developed to monitor and gather data for any other application. Shiny4SelfReport can be adapted to economic activities at sea or on land, or in other fields, surveys and sampling strategies.

Designed for usability and flexibility, Shiny4SelfReport **facilitates user engagement**. The app can be used with any spoken language, photos can replace species names, and selected species and variables can be displayed.

Instead of expensive software, Shiny4SelfReport uses common and **affordable technologies**.

Data management and storage can be directed to any cloud account, thus enhancing privacy and security by being independent of the app's developer.

The technology works in both IOS and Android systems.

To start using Shiny4SelfReport, scan the QR code below or go to triatlas.shinyapps.io/shiny4SelfReport

- **For any species**
- **In any language**
- **Easy data access**
- **Free use**

Reference

E. M. Noleto-Filho, R. Angelini, J. Steenbeek, A. R. Carvalho: New, flexible and open-source fisheries self-reporting app: The Shiny4SelfReport. *SoftwareX*, 16, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2021.100843>.

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